

Physiology and plant nutrition

Analysis of growth duration and heat units of different rice genotypes

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In general, higher temperatures accelerate the rate of development at all phenological stages of a crop and thereby reduce the length of a given phenological stage (Oldemann et al 1986).

We analyzed variation in duration of some prominent rice genotypes from sowing to 50% flowering and the corresponding variation in accumulated degree days (DD) (with base temperature of 10 °C) in Raipur, India. Long-term phenological observations and meteorological data from a nearby agrometeorological observatory were used.

Duration from sowing to 50% flowering of 12 selected genotypes varied from 66 d (Poorva) to 111 d (Surekha) [see table]. The

DD requirement for the same period was lowest for Poorva (1127 DD) and highest for Surekha (1935 DD). The coefficient of variation for duration varied from 2.6% for Samridhi to 6.8% for Cauvery, indicating least variability for Samridhi and greatest variability for Cauvery. Variability in DD requirement varied from 4.8% for Samridhi to 6.9% for Phalguna. For Samridhi, this indicates that variability in duration was lower than variation in DD requirement. This is contrary to the general belief that variability in duration of different phenological stages can well be explained by DD.

This trend also suggests that variability in duration of different phenological stages is influenced more by thermal regime within the vicinity of the crop environment. The meteorological observatory was situated in a nearby field and the microclimate there is quite different from the one existing in the ricefields.

Cited reference

Oldemann LR, Seshu DV, Cady FB. 1986. Response of rice to weather variables. Report on the IRRI/WMO Project. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. ■

The processes of pollination and fertilization in rice

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The processes of pollination and fertilization in higher plants have, to date, been only well studied in Liliaceae species.

In japonica rice variety Nipponbare, we observed conditions of pollen tube elongation on the stigmatic hair and the portion of the style through which the pollen tube passed. Pollen tube behavior in the ovary was also studied. At the flowering stage, every flower was sampled and fixed in formalin-acetic-alcohol after pollination. These samples were examined under both fluorescent and light microscopes after being sectioned using a resin-embedding method.

Light microscopy of a cross-section taken from the top of the stigma to the bottom of the ovule showed that each stigmatic hair had a hole in the center (the intercellular space formed with stigmatic hair cells) (Fig. 1a). These holes are connected to an area (transmitting tissue) made up of cells that are shaped differently than other parenchymatous cells located inside the vascular bundle of the stigma (Fig. 1b). This area continued through the stylar tissue up to the ovary. In the ovary, a narrow space was observed between the outer wall of the ovule and the ovary wall, except at the dorsal portion of the locule (Fig. 1c). This space shows where the pollen tube passed through the micropyle. The longitudinal sections of the ovary reveal that the ovary wall and the outer wall of the ovule fused from the top to near the bottom of the ovule (Fig. 1d).

Analysis of variation in growth duration (from germination to 50% flowering) and degree days of some prominent rice genotypes.

Variety	Observations (no.)	Duration (d from germination to 50% flowering)			Accumulated degree days		
		Mean	SD	Cv (%)	Mean	SD	CV (%)
IR36	31	92	4.95	5.4	1584	100	6.3
Samridhi	6	89	2.33	2.6	1527	73	4.8
Poorva	12	66	4.35	6.6	1127	65	5.8
Tripti	16	76	4.6	6.1	1311	81	6.1
Cauvery	25	75	5.1	6.8	1295	81	6.2
Deepti	13	91	4.6	5.0	1575	89	5.6
Ratna	41	89	4.9	5.5	1539	86	5.6
Madhuri	10	105	5.3	5.0	1794	115	6.3
Anupama	38	88	4.7	6.4	1523	94	6.1
Phalguna	24	104	5.9	5.7	1771	123	6.9
Surekha	9	111	5.6	5.0	1935	113	5.8
Usha	8	102	5.7	5.6	1762	91	5.1

1. Observations of some parts of the rice pistil using a light microscope. a) cross-section of a stigmatic hair, b) cross-section of a stigma, c) cross-section toward the bottom of an ovary, and d) longitudinal section of the dorsi-ventral direction of an ovary. Bars show 100 µm.

2. Observations of some parts of the rice pistil after pollination using an epifluorescence microscope. a) cross-section of stigmatic hair, b) longitudinal section of stigmatic hair, c) cross-section of the uppermost part of style, and d) cross-section of ovary. Bars show 100 µm.

Fluorescent microscopy showed that pollen germination occurred 1 h after the pollen reached the stigmatic hairs. The pollen tube then elongated, passing through the center hole of the stigmatic hair (Fig. 2a, b). In the stigmatic and stylar tissues, the pollen tube passed through the transmitting tissue located in the space between the center area and the vascular bundle (Fig. 2c). (Among Liliaceae species, the pollen tube is believed to pass through the stylar cavity.)

The cells comprising the transmitting tissue differed from other parenchymatous cells. They appear as a darkened area under the fluorescent microscope, implying that the cells were thin walls. The absence of a narrow space toward the dorsal side (downward) of the ovary explained the observation of pollen tube elongation at both sides of the locule but not in the dorsi-ventral direction of the ovary (Fig. 2d).

The pollen tube reached the micropyle 3 h after pollination. However, time of fertilization could not be determined. ■

Studies on intercellular space of embryo and seedling tissues in rice plants

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The development of intercellular spaces into aerenchyma in rice plants is thought to be important in improving oxygen gas diffusion through the plant body. But details of the developmental process during seedling and early vegetative stages are unclear. To better understand the process, a morphological study of intercellular spaces was conducted using high-resolution microscopy as well as cryo-scanning electron microscopy.

Intercellular spaces form in mature embryos of dry seeds (see figures a, b, c).

The spaces are located mainly in the parenchymatous cell regions including the scutellum, mesocotyl, and coleoptile and radicle, and are evident in the inner regions of these tissues. Intercellular spaces near the apical region of the radicle procortex were found in mature embryos, confirming previous findings (Armstrong 1979) (see figures f, g). However, all these spaces, which appear at the corner of neighboring cells, are very small in dry seeds. They increase in volume during imbibition and germination (see figures a-e).

During the early seedling stages after germination, no obvious changes in intercellular space were observed, but a tubular structure along the longitudinal cell alignment was formed (this occurred after the elongation and development of cortical cells along the shoot-root axis) (see figures e, f, h). In the shoot region, air space was formed in chlorenchymatous cell regions in the coleoptile and young leaves, especially under nonsubmerged culture condition.

The intercellular space near the axis during the early seedling stage seemed to be mostly in the water-rich state as revealed by cryo-scanning electron microscopy. Similar results have been obtained in other plants (Canny and Huang 1993). Seven days after germination, root air space was formed in the basal elongated seminal root region of the nonsubmerged plants. In the submerged condition, inner air space was formed among the elongated coleoptile and young leaves, while seminal root growth was reduced and the development of the cortical air space was delayed.

Cited references

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 Canny MJ, Huang CX. 1993. What is in the intercellular spaces of roots? Evidence from the cryo-analytical-scanning electron microscope. *Physiol. Plant.* 87:561-568. ■